

EXAMINING THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN UNIVERSITY IMAGE, STUDENT EXPERIENCE, AND EDUCATIONAL VALUE PERCEPTION, THROUGH THE LENSES OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING AND VALUE CREATION ACTIVI- TIES – THE CASE OF A UNIVERSITY’S COMPETI- TIVNESS

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RESEARCH CONTEXT

Transnational education (TNE) has been implemented for decades worldwide and very often the term “blended learning” is used to refer to this form of training. In TNE, the delivery of educational service products (e.g., academic programs) is done in a remote country other than the original one where the awarding institution is located. The typical forms of TNE can be observed as distance learning, joint ventures (overseas branch campuses), franchise, dual degrees, fly-in faculty, or the mixture. The market for higher education TNE offers is increasing both in scale and strategic importance. Many international universities employ TNE as their key strategic approach to reach the offshore markets globally. In large emerging markets such as Indonesia and Vietnam, it is noticeable that there has been a shift towards in-country provision. For examples, the ‘campus within a campus’ model in Vietnam, and four branch campuses in Indonesia (three from Australia, and one joint venture between Lancaster University and Deakin University) are observable (Acumen, 2024). The next wave of TNE in Southeast Asia may happen in Vietnam as an emerging player due to the capacity and quality constraints in the local education system and the appetite for international education. Joint Training Programs (JTPs) led by institutions from the UK, US, Australia and France is the traditionally TNE delivery models in Vietnam. 70% of those are undergraduate programs, mainly business and STEM majors (Acumen, 2024).

PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Viewing a university a service organization (environment) with educational service products, the author of this study is planning to choose a *private and local Vietnam-based university operating TNE programs* to examine the **three inter-connected factors** including: **(1) university image, (2) student experience, and (3) educational value perception**. To do this, the author will explore through the lenses of **activities related to experiential marketing and value creation** at the chosen university. Those activities practically influence each or in combination of the three factors at various intensity. As a result, the competitiveness of the university is dependent on them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Higher education institutions (HEIs) have utilized branding as a means of differentiating themselves from one another (Pinar et al., 2020). Universities have turned to brand initiatives to deal with commercial pressures (Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016; and Weinstein and Mcfarlane, 2017). Ansary and Hashim (2018) argued that customers are generally loyal to a few brands at a given time. Sustainable branding is therefore necessary to create unique product experiences for consumers to maintain their loyalty. Many service companies have worked to strengthen their brands through *brand components (identity, image and reputation)*, which are not confined to physical products. Brand identity, brand image, and brand reputation are separate constructs but interchangeably used by researchers. It is identified that brand image and brand identity are the components of brand reputation (Bankins and Waterhouse, 2019).

Students are increasingly being treated as customers by HEIs around the world, and this trend has led to an increase in marketing-oriented HEIs (Alam et al., 2016; and Guilbault, 2018). Consumers' purchase decisions are heavily influenced by factors other than brand equity such as *image of the brand* (Ansary and Hashim, 2018). Having **a strong brand image** can help differentiate a particular brand from its competitors, due to positive associations and assessments in the minds of consumers, which in turn *contributes to brand equity* (Ansary and Hashim, 2018).

There is evidence that *brand image has a substantial impact on brand equity* in many industries (Ali et al., 2016). Brand image enables customers to identify their relevant demands and grasp the brand's effective mechanism for delivering on their needs. (Pinar et al., 2020). The unified effort of a brand name to be remembered by customers relative to the attributes of other brands is known as brand image (Ansary and Hashim, 2018). Customers' opinions of a brand are based on its image in the marketplace (Keller, 2016). People's perceptions of a brand's image have been examined earlier (Papadopoulos and Hamzaoui-Essoussib, 2015;

Alam et al., 2016; and Ali et al., 2016). According to Chinomona (2016), consumers respond favorably to brands that have distinct and strong brand images (Anselmsson et al., 2014; and Jumiaty and Norazah, 2015), and students are no exception (Goia et al., 2014).

Universities that have positive brand image can differentiate themselves and gain competitive advantage by *building positive reputation*. A university's reputation is based on its ability to convey a clear picture of the university's past, present and future possibilities to its stakeholders (Azeem et al., 2019). Hence, university reputation is assessed by the perception of students, staff and the public, which allows for comparison and distinction of various characteristics of the university (Qazi et al., 2021). The university's proud tradition, positive opinion of quality of service, and a sense of trust can all help build a positive brand image for the institution (Alam et al., 2016).

From a brand perspective, TNE creates opportunities for education institutions to go beyond their home base and reach new destinations (host countries). Quality assurance is the crucial component in the delivery of TNE programs. It can be narrowed down to *student experience* and positive influence brand integrity. Following that positive word of mouth and recommendations can emerge to attract new students (Knight & Liu, 2017).

The concept of student experience, like university reputation, *originates from the adaptation of the customer experience concept, defined as the "journey" a customer takes with a product or service, focusing on the cognitive, emotional, behavioral, sensory, and social responses of a customer to a company's offerings* (Lemon and Verhoef, 2016). In the context of higher education, student experience refers to *the value* a student derives from their overall university life (D'Uggento et al., 2023), considering that education is an experience that *cannot be evaluated until it is experienced*.

The student journey begins with their choice of program, where they are recognized as customers, and extends through their role as students and co-creators of knowledge, until their completion as graduates of the academic programs offered by the university (Amado et al., 2023)

The construct of student experience also shares the characteristic of being multi-dimensional (Lemon and Verhoef, 2016). Studies such as Chandra et al. (2018) have identified that enhancing student experiences is important as they are linked to the quality of educational services. *Student Experience (SX)* received more attention and examination. SX is not new in the education sector. Universities have thought about it in their strategic agendas, but it is now ever important to the sustainability of universities if they can build great SX. The thing is SX is not in

line with the best practices of contemporary *Customer Experience (CX)* as witnessed in the service sectors. Facing disruption and increased competition, worldwide institutions now need to rethink SX (King & McCullough, 2021).

Researchers in Higher education agreed that *SX cannot be a pure carbon copy of CX in business services* applied to education. Students and universities establish relationships in unique and multi-faceted nature. Great SX must be designed to meet the whole student. This implies that universities need to treat any student as a mixture of a learner, a person, and a customer. Therefore, SX is broader and more complex than CX alone (King & McCullough, 2021). *The components of SX consists of first CX which means students*, as the customers, need to receive what they expect upon transacting with the institution and be impressed by the services provided during university life. Loyalty can be formed. Second, *personal experience (PX)* which means it should be appropriate to the specific circumstance of the student and able to build a unique relationship with the university. Third, *learning experience (LX)* which means it should suit the learning styles and maximize the actual learning of the student. Thus: $SX = LX + PX + CX$ (King & McCullough, 2021).

Despite various research efforts into the *concept of perceived value*, challenges regarding different interpretations in the literature persist (Amado et al., 2023). University leaders encounter the challenges of developing value-centered management strategies for *students' perceived value* (Pinna et al., 2023), where students evaluate their educational journey based on what they give and what they receive in return (Usman and Mohd, 2017). For the purposes of this study, perceived value by the student will result from their experience, evaluated through tangible and intangible elements of the educational service. It will be measured based on the importance each student assigns to these elements, considering a balance between positive perceptions of what they receive from the university and the economic efforts and dedication they invest.

Perceived value is a multidimensional construct highly correlated with other variables. For instance, the study by Doña-Toledo et al. (2017) demonstrated that quality determines perceived value, which in turn determines satisfaction. One of the main benefits of educational service perceived value is that it enables students to build trust and loyalty toward the institution (Hashim et al., 2015). It implies, based on preference, the outcome of a received compensation and an interaction between the student and the institution. Other studies, such as the one conducted by Shahijan et al. (2018), found that *the total experience* of international students in both public and private universities influences individually perceived value. It is also noted that the experience can be social, emotional, or physical. On the other hand, a study by Doña-Toledo et al. (2017) investigated the value perceived by graduates, considering their initial expectations versus the university experience. The study discovered that the perceived quality of the university experience had

a significant influence on graduates' perceived value. Focusing on designing effective educational programs requires continuous and *adequate monitoring of students' perceptions of their educational experience* (de Oliveira Silva et al., 2020). It was also found that students' experience in a particular course was valued considering previous experiences, which influenced the value perceived by students (Jones et al., 2017).

Marketing activities have a significant influence on decisions related to repurchase, word-of-mouth transmission of experiences, satisfaction and loyalty, among other behaviors (Doña-Toledo et al., 2017). *Experiential marketing* concept is developed from the CX concept. The customer's involvement is necessary in experiential marketing activity aiming to exceed the demands of the customer. In addition, it addresses the self-image, values, desires, and inactive emotions of an individual (Srinivasan and Srivastava, 2010). Pine and Gilmore (1999) also supported the involvement of customers and highlighted the greater importance of experience in experiential marketing. They compared and claimed the attachment of customers and experiences to experiential marketing and differentiates it from the traditional marketing which focuses on the product. They stated that experiential marketing goes beyond the purpose of providing goods and services meeting the customer's demands. It can offer unique, memorable, and personalized experiences to the customer.

Schmitt (1999b) elaborated further by associating experiential marketing with brands and companies. The author claimed that *experiential marketing is a communications method* assisting customers to sense, feel, think, act. He then developed five different types of experiences and named the strategic experiential modules (SEMs): "sensory experiences (SENSE), affective experiences (FEEL), creative cognitive experiences (THINK), physical experiences and entire lifestyles (ACT), and social identity experiences that result from relating to a reference group or culture (RELATE)" (Schmitt, 1999a: 53).

The SEMs help an organization to stage holistic experiential activity and elicit emotional response with the brand. In other words, the customer is immersed with the experience (Schmitt, 2003). The emotional response is effective in terms of developing engagement, empowerment, memorable moments, and unforgettable feelings. That means the trust and loyalty from customers are conquered (Li and Yang, 2010). Experiential marketing that is applied by universities can be created through the five distinct types of experiences for customers called *strategic experiential modules (SEMs): Sense, Feel, Think, Act, and Relate*. It is realistic and practical to *employ experiential marketing in HE, specifically the university environment*. By viewing students as customers, the concept of customer experiences is applicable to enhance the competitiveness of a university. Moreover, the value creation and the formation of perceptions inside the mind of students also contribute to the success of the experiential marketing approach.

Marketing communication plays a crucial role in enhancing the interaction and shaping the brand image. Successful interactions with positive experiences not only give competitiveness but also help build brand image. At the top layer, the aims of marketing communication are to announce, train, make believe, make think of, yield action, and form human connections. Moreover, marketers (at universities) can choose either strategic or tactical approaches. Normally, a combination of both is favorable. Service firms (universities with educational services) will try to communicate to their prospective customers (students) that they are superior in offering certain service products. In this sense, their efforts are to draw the new (prospective students) and to nurture the established connection with old customers (alumni). If the intention is tactical, at any stage of the service consumption process marketers (at universities) can elicit actions, shape, and manage perceptions, beliefs, or attitudes of the prospects. Any communication effort can be done with specific objectives to deal with any features related to customer (student) behaviors in service marketing. For example, communicating quality via promotion of tangible signals or adding value through communication content (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2016).

IDENTIFIED GAPS

It is observed that the primary topics of the current TNE research are surrounding: (i) management and development issues; (ii) trends and challenges; (iii) quality assurance; (iv) addressed policies/regulations; (v) student issues; (vi) faculty perspectives, outcomes and impact, pedagogy and curriculum, rationales, and definitions. Management issues and quality assurance are obviously important and encouraging but it can be a trouble if little attention has been spent on outcomes and impact as well as pedagogy and curriculum (Knight & Liu, 2017). There are still plenty of rooms for research on the different modes and dimensions of TNE as it is worth exploring the evolving reality like TNE.

Although TNE sector is still growing in scale, scope, and complexity, it has not been given enough attention in Higher Education research. Under the view of TNE as the mode of program provider and mobility, research on TNE gives references to international branch campuses (IBCs); partnership programs (involving collaboration between host and sending countries such as twinning and joint/double degree program); joint universities (binational, cofounded, and codeveloped institutions); franchise programs (export programs from sending countries); and multi-mode/generic. Most focuses are on the IBC modes which reflect geographic factors. Furthermore, the perspectives from the sending countries are dominant and those from host countries are under-represented. That can be worrisome (Knight & Liu, 2017). From the literature reviews, the author of this study has identified that most studies in HE followed quantitative methods to explore the relationships

between isolated variables by constructing hypotheses. The most observed is between 2 variables. For example, a positively perceived service quality will positively influence the university image. There was rare to investigate 3 or more in combination.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Having highlighted the importance of student experience, university image, perceived value, experiential marketing activities, value creation, and communications in the TNE context. The aims of this study are:

1. To explore the impacts of experiential marketing and value creation activities on:
 - a. building a differentiated brand image of a university, with positive associations of service quality, trust, and meanings
 - b. shaping positive students' value perception of tangible and intangible aspects of the educational services delivered by the studying university, and
 - c. staging memorable experiences which in turn positively influence the integrity of university image and the perceived value, during the student journey.
2. To investigate the effectiveness of current communications employed by the university. Specifically, the communication channels will be limited to:
 - ✓ social media (Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube),
 - ✓ mass media like TVs (education) or local radio broadcasts, and
 - ✓ official websites managed by the university.

The format of communication materials can be:

- ✓ printed or published materials (hardcopy)
 - ✓ video, sound, text, livestreams, reels, stories, news, or talk shows (depending on the selected channel).
3. To identify the key drivers, patterns, and preferences of student experience emerging during the student journey.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the identified problems and research objectives, the author of this study develops the below research questions:

1. (a) How has the university image of the concerned university been established?
(b) Also, how may such an image influence the preferences and attitudes or behaviors of the students?

2. How do the students (current and alumni) perceive the educational value of studying at the concerned university?
3. How may marketing communications contribute to creating memorable student experiences? and university image?
4. How has the student experience been created and changed throughout the student journey?

STUDY DESIGN/METHOD/APPROACH

APPROACH

The author of this study decides to employ Qualitative Case Study due to the following reasons: this study involves complex business relationships within the university environment and established networks so the selection of a case study with critical realism is appropriate. The author of this study would like to explore the multiple and interconnected factors happening in real time and in natural context where the differences can be exposed (Kaarbo & Beasley, 1999). A case study is relevant to dig deep into the students' thoughts to understand the attached meanings (Creswell, 2013). The qualitative perspective allows students and related participants to "use their own words to draw on their own concepts and experiences" (Orlikowski & Baroudi, 1991). A qualitative case study, various data sources and lenses are accepted to create multiple facets of the issues being investigated (Baxter & Jack, 2008).

The author of this study does not intend to test theories; therefore, a case study to discover the involved processes (the student journey since the beginning). It is possible that new hypotheses and information are added to the literature of HE practices of marketing. Students will be approached in a natural setting to discover what must be known. The aim is to investigate patterns revealing evidence of interaction among stakeholders within the university environment. Those will be emerged after observation, careful documentation, and thoughtful interpretation of the empirical data.

PARTICIPANTS

The author is going to select *University of Economics and Finance (UEF)* in *Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam* which is the best selection for this study. The university is running TNE programs. However, at this stage of the study, there has not been official permission from UEF yet. The distinctive characteristic of UEF is that it is a young, dynamic university, bilingual, and completely owned by the Vietnamese management board. The university is ambitious to become an excellent and truly international standardized serving for the Vietnamese students first and further the Southeast Asia region. The administration and international collaboration

at UEF are more open-minded and effectiveness oriented. The author of this study realizes the university is doing better things not only in building its university brand image but also in attracting Vietnamese students. In brief, the author of this study has witnessed the marketing activities are done more creatively. That means, UEF combines and utilizes resources effectively with student experience in mind. Marketing communication at UEF with interesting contents and events have been implemented with higher frequency, compared with other universities. All are prepared and presented to the public professionally. One interesting thing is the co-jointed activities between university staff and students to co-create meaningful values both academically, interpersonally, and socially. Of course, those are accompanied by supporting communications to boost the UEF image nicely.

Intended Interviewees	Total Number (not the same as in the pilot study)
Student	30
At UEF, there are also exchange students from foreign countries. So, the author will try to diverse the profiles beside the majors	
University Staff	25
The author of this study plans to interview:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>The head of faculty, office, institute, center, or union (5 to 6 people)</i> ▪ <i>Vietnamese lecturers or professors (3 to 6 people)</i> ▪ <i>Foreign lecturers or professors (3 to 6 people)</i> ▪ <i>Others (4 to 7 people)</i> 	

Figure 1. Interviewees Overview

ETHICAL ISSUES AND CONSIDERATION

Ethical considerations are very critical to any research. It is imperative that proper steps are taken to ensure that participants are fully aware of their participation and role. To safeguard the participants' rights and firms' information, the following steps will be employed in this study:

The name of the selected university is not named in the report due to respect for its reputation and to avoid unnecessarily explicit indication or reference.

The privacy and confidentiality of the selected university and individuals are protected during and after the research process.

Participants were provided with consent forms and information sheets.

There was no deception at any stage in the research process. Participants were made fully aware of what was expected.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The author is going to use: (1) in-depth interviews and (2) communication materials to support the data collection, manipulation, and analysis.

In-depth interviews are chosen because it allows the author to understand how and why the students at the investigated university hold a particular view about an issue (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). In social science research, interviews are widely used, and most participants are familiar and comfortable. The author can get informed consents, reduce time and efforts to train or brief participants procedures and commitments (Miller and Crabtree, 1999). Through the students or relate participants' words, they can have direct access to their thoughts and understand the real-life actions or experiences being reflected (King, 2004a; Silverman, 2010).

The selection of communication channels and formats of communication materials are mentioned in the research objective (2) above. The communication contents and their influences on the experiences, the perceptions, and the university image are the most concerned to analyze. It will be an exhausting task to collect too many communication items where each item is a combination of channel, tool, format, who is the owner, and details. Therefore, the author will be very selective with his combination and figure out what is worth collecting and combining. Tentatively, the starting number can be 10 items.

The interview questions are designed to elicit responses from students surrounding the dimensions as shown in the following figure:

Notes on data collection from interviews	
Themes	Dimensions
Student Experience	<i>Student-centered service</i>
	<i>Diversity and global citizenship</i>
	<i>Co-production of the learning experience</i>
	<i>Teacher/lecturer/professor dependence</i>
	<i>Accountability</i>
	<i>Whole-person development</i>
Perceived Value	<i>Functional</i>
	<i>Epistemic</i>
	<i>Social</i>
	<i>Emotional</i>
	<i>Non-monetary sacrifices</i>
	<i>Monetary sacrifices</i>
	<i>Image</i>
University Image	<i>Cost</i>
	<i>Social Responsibility</i>
	<i>Reputation</i>
	<i>Academic services</i>
	<i>Student services and university environment</i>
	<i>Administrative services</i>
	<i>Information technology services</i>
	<i>Student demographics and characteristics</i>

Figure 2. Notes on Data Collection from Interviews

Figure 3. Data Collection and Coding

The pilot study process will be conducted to preliminarily understand the main issues of concerns (Gummesson, 2000), to be familiar with the context and the subject, and to identify possible structures, contents, or relevant aspects. The author of this study revisited previous studies done, as suggested by Hart (1998) in the HE to get references. The author of this study plans to conduct 10 interviews in the pilot study. The pilot study was proven to be useful as it allowed the researcher to identify issues related to the interview process and protocol. The main outcome from this pilot study gives more input to revise interview protocol and to refine the initial coding scheme (template) for data analysis. Through the pilot study, the author himself can recognize other missing components to operate his study and do modifications.

The author has found the *NVivo software* an excellent tool for data analysis. The methods employed for analyzing are: (1) the *template analysis* (for in-depth interviews), and (2) the *qualitative relational content analysis* (for communication materials and data from in-depth interviews). A brief procedure for template analysis is shown in the flow chart above. **For relational content analysis, the author will go through 7 steps:** (1) *Choose samples for analysis*, (2) *Determine the type of analysis*, (3) *Reduce to categories and code for words or patterns*, (4) *Explore the relationship between concepts*, (5) *Code the relationship*, (6) *Apply statistical analysis*, and (7) *Map out representation*.

Coding is a very important step in the process of data analysis. Relevant codes will be attached to the transcripts. The author of this study will adopt the coding procedures suggested by Bazeley (2007), Saldana (2009) and Gibbs (2011). To ensure the reliability, careful and detailed preparation of the coding, there are two cycles: First, each transcript is coded using the pen and paper technique, based on the initial template. Relevant passages are marked with corresponding codes. Second, the transcript is imported into NVivo (a qualitative data analysis software). In the second cycle, the author does not refer to the codes in the first cycle but lets the software code again. This way will assist the author to figure out some themes he may have missed.

Each code will have a definition which is called a node in NVivo. This is done to help the author understand what the code refers to and the context of using it. A codebook with definitions is needed. The coding process will then be consistent for the author. The codes from a single transcript are organized in a hierarchy called tree nodes in Nvivo. Gibbs (2011, pp. 47 - 48) suggested the categorization of codes as below:

- (i) **Specific acts, behaviors** – what the interviewee's do or say.
- (ii) **Events** – usually brief, one-off events or things someone has done.
- (iii) **Activities** – longer duration than acts and often take place in a particular setting and may have several people involved.
- (iv) **Strategies, practices or tactics** - activities aimed towards some goal
- (v) **States** – general condition experienced by people or found in organizations.
- (vi) **Meanings** – concepts, norms, values, rules, or symbol used by participants to understand their world and its significance to them
- (vii) **Participation** – people's involvement or adaptation to a setting.
- (viii) **Relationship or interaction** - between people, considered simultaneously.
- (ix) **Conditions or constraints** – the precursor to or cause of events or actions. Things that restricted behavior or actions
- (x) **Consequences**
- (xi) **Setting** – the entire context of the event under study.

Figure 4. Categorization of Codes

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

This study does not intend to generalize the findings but to interpret the concerned issues so generalizability, a common criterion to assess research study is not applicable Merriam (2002). Each interpretation is unique and impossible to replicate meaning that reliability and generalizability are irrelevant for this present study in terms of qualitative method. raised the concern about “how congruent are one’s findings with reality?”. One of the strategies adopted to increase reliability in the present study was the use of two cycles of coding (Saldana, 2009) for each transcript which has been described in coding system.

Due to the iterative processes of data collection and analysis, the author of this study will make frequent decisions that can change the course of the study. Therefore, it is important to maintain a document keeping notes on the steps and decisions taken to come up with the research findings (King, 2007). The author is going to keep a research diary. Some entries related to data analysis can be imported to NVivo using the memo tool. Each revision will be given a new name to distinguish, and it is easier to keep track of changes made. The validity of this study may be affected by the involvement of the author in shaping the findings (King, 2007). His previous similar experience and presuppositions regarding the issues may impact his interpretation. Therefore, it is necessary to be reflexive throughout the whole research process. The author needs to highly be aware that biases can happen and not to conclude without completed analysis. A research diary is effective to manage risks. Another issue that may arise is that the interviewees might feel obligated to only share positive aspects. Hence, they were reminded that their inputs, either positive or negative, were all important for the research.

FINDINGS AND ORIGINALITY/VALUE

For the moment, the author of this study is preparing for real data collection and the pilot study. Therefore, no analysis has been done. It is not the right time to examine the findings and to interpret.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

Students themselves are changing and more demanding in the experience they will receive from their universities. The trend is that the next generation of students will become more diverse, digital, discerning, demanding and debt averse. World-wide universities are likely to be too confident in their current student centricity and lack of preparation for the future challenges where the volatile and complex of the authorizing and operating environment will present. Universities can encounter obstacles from legacy cultures, systems, policies, fragmented data, and low invested CX development. So, there is room for improvement.

The 2020s with the changes in technology, demography, global rebalancing of power and wealth, and the age of the customer will greatly influence the education industry. However, not all the changes just mentioned will be factored into the universities' planning. To remain competitive, each university will need to develop their own 'SX factor'. The universities that can: (i) serve diversity at scale; (ii) deliver rich digital learning and engagement; (iii) design service platforms in line with student expectations; (iv) partner with the individual student to co-create an education and engagement experience; (v) understand and serve students' preferences; and (vi) do so at a competitive cost, will both survive and thrive.

This study potentially contributes to the practice of marketing educational services by supplementing a different perspective of how to facilitate activities related to experiential marketing and value creation for students, where a university serves as a service organization and the student experience concept goes further the mere application of the customer experience concept. By understanding the connection between the 3 factors: student experience, university image, and value perception together with the reveals form the analyses of collected data, the university can see what is doing well and what needs improvement for communication, for designing appropriate student experiences, for aligning and co creating value with the student expectations, both at the tactic and strategic level.

The perceived service quality of education and cultural dimensions are inevitable and influencing on the university image student experience. However, this study is not going to extend to those. Therefore, future research can elaborate on those. Moreover, the author does notice that new IT technology and digital platforms influence significantly the Higher Education in terms of: (a) delivering core edu-

ational services (students as customers and associated CX); (b) learning experiences (LX), and (c) personal experiences. Due to limited time, the author will not integrate those aspects into this study. This gives room for separate research with more deeper investigating the associated technological factors.

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